

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

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No. 34

• Australia

First record of dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium catenatum* Graham (1943) from Lakes Entrance, Gippsland Lakes, Australia

Gymnodinium catenatum Graham (1943) was first recorded in Australia from Tasmanian waters in 1980 [1]. Dating of cysts in sediments from the Huon River suggests an introduction date to Tasmania of around 1973 [2]. Vegetative cells and/or cysts have since been recorded from several mainland sites (Fig. 1) [3, 4]. The new finding brings the number of affected Australian bioregions to 12. This is the only algal species on the Australian Quarantine and Inspection Service (AQIS) Marine Target list recorded in the Gippsland Lakes [5].

The Gippsland Lakes (~270 km east of Melbourne) comprise a system of

shallow, estuarine lagoons, occupying a former coastal embayment now separated from the Tasman Sea (east of Bass Strait) by long, narrow sandy barriers that form part of the Ninety Mile Beach. They have a surface area of approximately 360 km² and comprise three main lakes: Wellington, Victoria and King. The catchment drains an area of 20,600 km², about 12% of Victoria's land mass, through five major river systems. A permanent entrance to the sea was established in 1889 at the eastern end of the lakes, at the town of Lakes Entrance (Figs. 1 and 3).

Monthly sampling for dinoflagellates began in the Gippsland Lakes in 2001,

as part of an RMIT University PhD project on HAB species. Weekly sampling began in February 2006 for the Environment Protection Agency (EPA) and the Department of Sustainability and Environment (DSE) as part of an expanded Cyanobacteria and HAB monitoring program. In January, 2007, a live (non-preserved) two-cell chain resembling *G. catenatum* (Fig. 2) was analysed by light microscopy from an area of Lakes Entrance known as the Warm Holes (Fig. 3). Cell width is ~38 µm. The surface is covered by amphismal vesicles. The deep girdle groove has a displacement of 1/3 – 1/4

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• New Zealand

Massive *Karenia mikimotoi* bloom in Northland, New Zealand: Use of traditional and molecular techniques for rapid identification of HAB species

Fig. 1. Lugol's preserved *K. mikimotoi* cell from Te Tii (Northland, NZ). Scale bar = 5 µm

In April 2007 water sampling was initiated by Northland Health Protection Officers after complaints by the public of red water discolouration, and fish and eel deaths in the water around Te Tii in the Te Puna Inlet near Kerikeri (Fig. 2). At the time of sampling (17 April 2007) the red discolouration could no longer be seen, but preserved (Lugol's solution) samples were sent to the Cawthron Institute's Microalgae Laboratory (Nelson) for analysis. *Karenia* cf. *mikimotoi* was identified under the light microscope as the organism producing

the bloom, with cell counts over 7.6 x 10 cells L⁻¹ (Fig. 2). Species in the genus *Karenia* can be difficult to distinguish from each other under the light microscope [1] and are identified as *Karenia* cf. *mikimotoi* for the New Zealand Non-Commercial Marine Biotoxin Monitoring Programme [2]. This term encompasses the following species: *Karenia bidigitata*, *K. brevisulcata*, *K. mikimotoi*, *K. papilionacea* and *K. selliformis*.

Preserved samples were analysed

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Fig. 2. Map of North Island, New Zealand showing bloom location, Te Puna Inlet, Northland region.

by real-time PCR and fluorescent *in situ* hybridisation (FISH) for a range of species from the *Karenia* genus. Real-time PCR assays were used to detect for *K. mikimotoi*, *K. brevisulcata*, *K. umbella*, *K. papilionacea* and *Takayama tasmanica*, and FISH assays to detect for *K. mikimotoi*, *K. brevisulcata*, *K. brevis*, *K. umbella*, *K. papilionacea*, *K. selliformis*, *Gymnodinium aureolum*, *Takayama* spp. (genus), and *T. tasmanica*. Samples analysed by real-time PCR showed that the sample was dominated by *Karenia mikimotoi*, with *T. tasmanica* present at very low levels. The preserved samples were successfully amplified in this real-time PCR assay and results were available the same day as sample receipt.

The FISH assay also confirmed the dominant organism as *K. mikimotoi*, however the results were more difficult to interpret as the Lugol's solution interfered with the fluorescent signal despite the addition of a decolourant. *Karenia* cells are also easily destroyed during the FISH process. The FISH assay could not detect the low numbers of *Takayama tasmanica* and analysis time was much longer than for the real-time PCR assay.

Further samples were collected on 19 April 2007 within Te Puna Inlet to determine the extent of the bloom. Live samples were analysed using *K. mikimotoi* probes with real-time PCR, FISH and sandwich hybridisation assay (SHA) formats. All produced positive results with analysis time for real-time

PCR and SHA much less than for FISH. At present we have not standardised and quantified the real-time PCR assay for *K. mikimotoi*. However, a standard curve relating optical density readings to cell counts using cultures of New Zealand isolates of *Karenia mikimotoi* has been calculated for SHA, enabling semi-quantification of results. The SHA targets ribosomal RNA (rRNA) and the concentration of rRNA per cell seems to be higher in field samples compared with cultures. From samples from the 2007 Northland bloom we were able to adjust our standard curve to more accurately reflect field samples.

Oyster and water samples taken from Te Puna Inlet were analysed by LC-MS/MS for brevetoxins (PbTx2 and PbTx3). No PbTx2 or PbTx3 was detected in the oyster or water sample by either method. The limit of detection for the LC-MS/MS method was <0.01 mg kg⁻¹ for the oyster flesh and <1ng/L for the water sample.

The bloom covered a moderately sized area as additional samples taken on the 19 April throughout the inlet were all positive for *K. mikimotoi* with counts in the millions of cells L⁻¹. Samples taken from a nearby site, Tapeka Point, had lower numbers of *K. mikimotoi* present (21,000 cells L⁻¹). Almost a month after the first visual sighting of the bloom, low numbers *K. cf. mikimotoi* cells (ca. 200 cells L⁻¹) were still being detected by light microscopy in samples collected at Kerikeri Inlet, near Te Puna. Specimens from the bloom were isolated and are now held in the Cawthron Microalgae Culture Collection.

The Northland area of New Zealand has previously experienced severe *K. mikimotoi* blooms. In 1992/93, 180 cases of illness that fit the symptoms of neurotoxic shellfish poisoning (NSP) occurred along the coast of Northland [3-5]. Brevetoxins and brevetoxin analogues were detected in shellfish samples causing the total closure of all bivalve industries in New Zealand [4]. The causative organism was initially tentatively identified as *K. cf. brevis* (previously *Gymnodinium cf. breve*), a species not detected in New Zealand previously. It is now known that *K. mikimotoi* was the dominant bloom species, and *K. brevis* remains

undetected in New Zealand waters to date [1].

In addition to brevetoxins, *K. mikimotoi* is known to produce hemolytic glycolipids [1] (that cause gill damage in fish and which have been linked to fish kills in Japan and Norway), and gymnocins A and B [6, 7], which are thought to be ichthyotoxic. The cause of the fish kills associated with the *K. mikimotoi* bloom in the Te Puna Inlet is not known. Oyster and water biotoxin screens by LC-MS were negative for brevetoxins and brevetoxin analogues.

Microalgal blooms can be associated with fish kills due to anoxia, a process that is intensified when a waterbody is stratified. Stratification can be caused by freshwater inputs to estuaries. Two weeks prior to the Te Puna bloom, Northland experienced extreme flooding which increased freshwater and nutrient inputs into the inlet. This is similar to the weather conditions preceding a large *K. mikimotoi* bloom in Irish waters in 2005 [8]. Rainfall averages for the month of the 2005 Irish bloom was almost double the 30-year average. High rainfall levels may have created favourable conditions for the formation of the 2007 Northland bloom and increased the rate of anoxia in the waterbody, resulting in associated fish kills.

By combining the use of traditional (light microscopy) and molecular methods, in particular real-time PCR and SHA, we were able to quickly identify that the bloom causing species was a potential neurotoxin producer and reliably confirm the identification to species level using a combination of molecular tools. The molecular methods were relatively quick and results were available the same day as sample receipt. Microscopy and molecular methods combine well to obtain a definitive species identification, avoiding a possible misclassification of *Karenia* species as occurred with the Northland 1992/93 bloom.

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of the cell length and the distinctive sulcus extends well into the epicone. Identification was confirmed from this image in August, 2007, by G. M. Hallegraeff and M. de Salas (UTAS, Hobart).

The Warm Holes (Fig. 3) are a series of five shallow pools, remnants of part of the original natural channel to the sea and now a central water-feature of the Lakes Entrance golf course. The navigable section of the original channel is known as Cunninghame Arm, which became a backwater following construction of the permanent entrance. The new entrance is located ~ 5-7 km west of the original natural opening. These ponds are similar in function to the retention ponds constructed as pollutant traps in housing – golf course developments along the South Carolina (USA) coast [6]. This functional similarity results in similar biological outcomes. The tidally restricted, nutrient-enriched ponds provide niche habitat for

potential HAB species including *Karlodinium veneficum*, *Karenia mikimotoi* and the cyanobacterium *Nodularia spumigena*.

Water quality at the time of sampling (Table 1) shows low dissolved oxygen (DO) and relatively high (although common at this site) chlorophyll *a* levels.

Depth (m)	°C	PSU	Chl <i>a</i> µg/L	DO%	pH
0.4	21.72	34	20	39.7	7.41

Salinity can approach ocean levels in 4 of the ponds and temperatures (16 °C mid-winter, 2007 Hole 4) are often higher than those found in the broader lake system (8-9 °C typical mid-winter). The Warm Holes are a significant spawning area for black bream (*Acanthopagrus butcheri*) an important commercial and recreational fish species. Occasional fish-kills are commonly ascribed to the effects of reduced DO levels, but investigative pathology has been limited.

Cunninghame Arm forms the main

harbour for a large commercial fishing fleet that operates outside the lakes in the south-east finfish trawl fishery. Prawns (*Melicertus plebejus*, *Metapanaeus macleayi*) are popular recreational species and are also taken commercially offshore. Mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) are harvested non-commercially for human consumption and fish-bait, from the main channel area outside Cunninghame Arm.

Two primary questions arise from the finding of *G. catenatum* in the estuary: (1) Will it be able to establish? (2) How did it get here – offshore ballast-water discharge, fishing boat bilge/ballast-water, fishing gear, coastal water currents, other?

The species has become well established in Tasmania [7], but mainland populations are ephemeral and vegetative cells and cysts are rarely reported. For instance, extensive cyst beds recorded at Lorne (south-west Victoria) in 1993 were not found again in a subsequent survey [8]. There are no reports of mainland events similar to the extensive Tasmanian blooms in the Huon and Derwent Estuaries (1986, 1991, 1993) that closed the shellfish industry for several months. Intriguingly, dating of Port Lincoln sediments [9] estimates introduction to this mainland site at around 1960 (± 20 yrs) or at least ~25 years ago, yet this population has also failed to thrive.

The reasons for the differences in population dynamics across Bass Strait are unclear. All Australasian isolates (and an isolate from the Seto Inland Sea, Japan) are considered genetically identical [7]. The consistent inability of *G. catenatum* to fully establish viable populations across a broad range of mainland habitats, including sheltered creeks, estuaries, bays and open coast, suggests more than simply a stochastic combination of adverse physical/

Fig. 1. *G. catenatum* sites: (1) Derwent River; (2) Triabunna; (3) Huon River; (4) Port Lincoln; (5) south-west Victoria six sites; (6) Port Philip Bay; (7) Bass River; (8) Port Welshpool; (9) Cowan Creek; (10) Bega coast; (11) Lakes Entrance. East Australian Current (EAC). (Images: Google Earth; NASA; TerraMetrics; Geoscience Australia)

Fig. 2. *G. catenatum*. Distinctive sulcus (arrow top) Amphiesmal vesicles (arrow bottom). Scale bar = 10 μ m.

chemical conditions.

Propagule pressure has been identified as a major determinant of species' invasion success [10]. Small populations are more likely to become extinct than larger ones and small populations are more vulnerable to environmental variation. Furthermore, declining populations can be fortified through repeated immigration and sub-populations spread across a number of habitats can mitigate the effects of adverse conditions on the whole population. Does this help explain the establishment pattern of *G. catenatum* in Australia?

The port of Triabunna (Tasmania) was opened for woodchip exports to Japan in 1971, around the estimated time of *G. catenatum* introduction (1973). It has operated more or less continuously since that time. Currently 800,000 tonnes of woodchips are exported annually through the port, equal to about 10 Cape size bulk carriers, each with a 50,000 tonne ballast-water potential. Mandatory ballast-water management was introduced in Australia in 2001, but even triple-flushing of ballast tanks at sea can leave around 5% of the original water, potentially equal to 2.75×10^9 cysts/ship [11] (and can create further problems depending on species present at the exchange site). Propagule pressure from 30 years of ballast water import at 10 or more visits per year (depending on ship size) would have been considerable.

Conversely, secondary invasion of mainland sites via ballast-water from Tasmania would have been restricted by: 1) size/type of vessels; 2) frequency of visits e.g. Drake & Lodge [12] conclude that reducing the number of ship visits is more effective in reducing the spread of species by ballast-water, than eliminating key "hotspot" ports; 3) need for carrying ballast i.e. goods are carried both ways; 4) probability of picking up live cells/cysts. Therefore the failure to fully establish on the mainland may be explained in part by low propagule pressure.

However, woodchips have been exported to Japan for over 35 years from the Port of Eden (Fig. 1) yet there is no

record of *G. catenatum* from the Eden sediments or water column. Different ballast-water management may explain this apparent anomaly, as deballasting was routinely conducted at sea prior to entering Eden harbour [13], thereby eliminating any propagule pressure.

Proximity of the Warm Holes to the ocean entrance and the boat harbour suggests 2 potential transport vectors: 1) enhanced coastal current intrusion during extended periods of low river-flow; 2) in-harbour vessel bilge/ballast water. The first hypothesis requires either a coastally-entrained inoculum/bloom, or an infected offshore ballast-water dump. Both are difficult to determine, although the East Australian Current (EAC) may play a role in transporting microalgae south from the mainland to Tasmania, and possibly westward to Lakes Entrance (e.g. the appearance of *K. papilionacea* in the eastern lakes in 2003). The directions of current flow and wind through Bass Strait alternate seasonally - west to east in winter; reverse in summer (typically, south-west fronts can appear at any time of the year). Therefore cysts or vegetative cells could potentially be transported from either direction. The second hypothesis may be tested to a limited extent by cyst/sediment surveys at wharf areas and tracking of vessel movements.

On the basis of propagule pressure, risk of establishment in the Gippsland Lakes would appear to be low, although the source of the cells is unknown and repetitive introductions remain possible. Even without the known history of activity at mainland sites, it is unlikely that *G. catenatum* would flourish throughout the lakes, due to the highly volatile salinity regime. However, cyst formation is a life-history adaptation that could facilitate establishment and opportunistic blooming, particularly in sheltered depositional areas around Lakes Entrance where cysts could accumulate, e.g. Warm Holes, Cunninghame Arm and North Arm (Fig. 3). If the species became established, other similar areas within the lakes could provide refugia for cyst accumulation and potential germination and should be monitored.

The finding of *G. catenatum* is a

Fig. 3. Warm Holes, Lakes Entrance (Lat. $37^{\circ} 52' 18''$ S - Long. $148^{\circ} 01' 33''$ E) Gippsland Lakes, Australia (Images: Google Earth; Geoscience Australia)

result of the RMIT University research project and the expanded EPA monitoring program, as no regular monitoring for phytoplankton species was previously conducted in the area.

Major flooding in June, 2007, brought about a reversal of a 10 year dry period, which had seen a steady increase in lake salinity (~0.2 PSU/year at eastern Lake King). However, saline water remains at depth throughout the eastern lakes and stratified conditions can favour dinoflagellate growth through vertical migration. The cycle of drought and flood is a characteristic of this climate and may become more extreme under global warming predictions. It remains to be seen how adaptable this species

will be to local climate variation and climate change in general.

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• Israel

Fish kill by *Prymnesium parvum* in the Arava Valley, Southern Israel

Fig. 1. Location where *Prymnesium parvum* bloom occurred (arrowed).

A bloom of the haptophyte *Prymnesium parvum* occurred in January 2007 in the Arava Valley, a desert area located in the south of Israel (Fig. 1), causing significant mortalities in an ornamental fish farm.

Continuous, 'creeping' mortalities in molly, *Poecilia* sp., and koi ('Japanese carp'), *Cyprinus carpio* ponds in this region started in 2003, when the system which uses water from local aquifers, was switched from flow-through to

closed circulation. The fish are grown in a variety of ponds (concrete, plastic-lined and earthen). Water temperature at the farm is maintained at $25 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$ and salinity of the inlet water fluctuates between 300 and 500 mg/l of chloride. Effluent water flows through a sedimentation pond and is then recirculated into the fish ponds. Whenever the salinity of the ponds rises to 700-1100 mg/l of chloride (1.3‰ - 2‰) due to evaporation, fresh well water is added.

Gross pathology, parasitological and histopathological analyses in a sample of about 20 molly and koi did not reveal the presence of pathogens or any particular abnormalities, as was also reported in similar cases by other authors [1, 2]. A microscopic examination of the water, however, revealed relative abundance (exceeding 1×10^5 cells/ml) of the haptophyte *Prymnesium parvum* (length $13.5 \mu\text{m} \pm 1.5$, width $9 \mu\text{m} \pm 1$) (Fig. 2). A bloom of the green microalga *Kirchneriella lunaris* was also observed, while the presence of diatom species of *Chaetoceros* and *Skeletonema*, and microflagellate species of *Cryptomonas* and *Chlamydomonas* was also detected. No mortality occurred in ten fish transferred into an aquarium with fresh, uncontaminated water and kept under

observation for over a month, indicating that the fish were in an initial and still reversible stage of intoxication, a feature already noted by other authors [3].

The system was treated with 10 ppm ammonium sulfate according to the recommendations of Reich and Aschner [1], and fish mortality ceased.

Outbreaks of this flagellate in Israel were first reported in the fall of 1945 [1]. Carp-stocked ponds in the Beisan (Beit She'an) Valley in the northern part of the country were affected. The condition gradually spread south and in the following winter reached the ponds of Beit-Ha'arava, a settlement north of the Dead Sea. This occurrence was not surprising, as although situated approximately 100 km apart, these two localities shared the same water supply.

Deterioration of water quality in aquaculture often creates conditions suitable to *P. parvum* blooming and consequent fish poisoning [2, 4, 5].

Aquifers in the southernmost part of Israel and mainly desert Arava Valley often yield brackish water, free of pollutants, that can be used to raise warm-water fish.

P. parvum propagation in this recent incident was quite clearly triggered by the up to three-fold increase in salinity, and favored by the moderately warm water of the fish pond and general

Fig. 2. *Prynnesium parvum*.

deterioration of recirculated water quality.

The renewed occurrence of *P. parvum* in this region is an unwelcome incident, which may require new management strategies to control its spreading.

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• Mexico

A bloom of *Noctiluca scintillans* and its possible cysts in the Gulf of California, Mexico

Marked discolorations were observed on 12-13 February 2007 at stations 13, 14 and 15, during Cruise Talud X in the central Gulf of California. The dominant taxon was *Noctiluca scintillans*, followed by *Pseudoeunotia doliolus*, *Chaetoceros* spp. and *Gymnodinium catenatum*. *Noctiluca* was counted in 50 ml surface samples settled for 24 hours [1]. Results (Fig. 1) were similar to those reported elsewhere (range 60 to 3720 cells L⁻¹) [2]. Surface temperature (17 to 18.9 °C) and salinity (35.1 to 35.3 PSU) data collected by CTD were within normal values for the season.

Most *Noctiluca* cells measured 200 to 800 µm diameter, corresponding to trophonts (Fig. 2A-B). Nevertheless, some cells resembling a gametogenic

event were also observed (Fig. 2C). The life cycle of *Noctiluca* consists of a vegetative stage (trophont) and a zoospore forming stage [3, 4]. Until recently, the fate of zoospores was unknown, but Fukuda and Endoh [5] describe the complete life cycle, showing the isogamic, homothallic nature of this process; there may also be anisogamy, if the zoospores are considered as microgametes. Some vegetative cells

look like macrogametes [6], a view sustained by an intermediate stage observed here (Figs. 2B, C, E); other specimens recall *Leptodiscus* sp. (Fig. 2D; Fig. 3B), identified for the first time in this region.

In some samples of this *Noctiluca* bloom, a structure resembling a cyst of great size was observed, spherical, 1.14 mm diameter, with triangles of 80 µm on each side all over the surface. On

Fig. 1. Abundance (cells L⁻¹) of *Noctiluca scintillans* in surface samples collected in Gulf of California, 10th to 15th February, 2007.

Figs. 2. *Noctiluca scintillans*. A) Two cells in vegetative stage (trophont). B) Gametocyte mother surrounded by small cells. C) Nucleated stage? D) Possible *Leptodiscacean*. E) Four different small specimens, scale bars 50 µm. Other scale bars 200 µm.

Fig. 3. Possible cyst of *Noctiluca*.

A) Spherical structure ornamented with small triangles of 80 µm on each side and projecting spines on vertices. A1) Detail of projections, which bear small spines near their ends. B) Possible *Leptodiscus*. C) Small trophont.

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the vertices of each triangle, a process projects outside bearing small spines distally (Figs. 3A-A1). To discard the possibility that we were dealing with a copepod egg, a thesis dealing with 16 species was reviewed and none showed a similar structure [7]. Furthermore,

copepods eggs are smaller than 250 µm in diameter. However, we cannot yet confirm that it is a cyst of *Noctiluca*.

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• Brazil

Bloom of *Alexandrium minutum* Halim on Rio de Janeiro coast: occurrence and toxicity

For the first time in the region, a major bloom of *Alexandrium minutum* Halim was observed off Rio de Janeiro Coast, 23 April 2007 (Fig. 1). Water discoloration was detected from 21st to 26th April, covering an extensive area including several beaches. The red to brownish water was fully evident to

beach goers, and reported in the newspapers.

Phytoplankton samples were collected on the 25th and later on 27th, when a surface sand sample was also taken from Leblon beach (Fig. 1). The cells from 250 L of the bloom water samples were concentrated in a 10 µm

Fig. 1. Map of Rio de Janeiro Coast showing the bloom area (open rectangles) and sample site (closed rectangle)

Figs 2-7. General morphology of *A. minutum* cells under light microscopy (bright field): (2) isolated live cells; (3) chains; (4) ventral view of clarified cell showing the reticulated pattern of hypotheca (arrow). Figs 5-7. Calcofluor stained cells under fluorescence microscopy: (5) ventral view of cell showing a conspicuous ventral pore (arrow); (6, 7) apical view of cell showing the apical pore complex (APC) (arrow) and the four apical plates ('). Scale bars = 20 μm (Fig. 2); 10 μm (Figs 3-7).

net to 500 ml. Part of the sample was fixed for identification and enumeration under microscopy and the remainder further concentrated and stored for toxin analysis. For the analysis of sand, 20 g was removed from a total of 1 K of collected sediment. From this, two aliquots of 1 mL were extracted, made up to 10 mL with filtered seawater, homogenized and filtered through 80 μm and 20 μm sieves, respectively. The slurry from each aliquot was made up with filtered seawater to a total of 10 mL. One aliquot was used for

counting and the other for morphological analysis.

The dissociated and clarified thecal plates were stained by Calcofluor[®] and observed under light and fluorescence microscope. The quantitative analysis was carried using settling chambers under an inverted microscope. A small pellet containing bloom cells was extracted with 0.1 N HCl under sonication and promptly analyzed for toxins, using the HPLC post column derivatization method of Oshima [1]. The peaks were compared to 10 available standards purchased from NRC/Canada.

Alexandrium minutum cells were found in the water and also in the sand samples. The samples showed the common phenotypic plasticity of vegetative morphological characters generally observed in natural populations [2-5]: cells usually solitary, or sometimes forming short chains of 2-4 cells; oval shaped to irregularly elliptic in dorsal view, with (17.1-) 19 - 31.2 (-32.3) μm long; 17.1 - 32.2 (-32.3) μm width (n = 100) (Figs. 2-7). The thecal formula is

Po, 4', 6'', 6C, 8S, 5''', 2''''', characteristic of *A. minutum*. The Po plate is directly connected through a channel to the pore less plate 1. The foramen is drop shaped and a ventral pore is clearly observed on plate 1'. The margins of the hypothecal sulcus generally present expansions resembling spines, and the posterior sulcal plate is without a pore. Most individuals (75%) showed a thick reticulate pattern with hypothecal *areolae*. Some cells showed irregular epithelial spacing similar to *striae*, and rare reticulate spacing.

Cell abundance ranged from 4.3 x 10⁵ to 1 x 10² cell L⁻¹ on April 25th and 27th respectively. Vegetative division was observed in samples from April 25th, while sexual reproduction, with consequent cyst formation was observed in water and sand samples collected on 27th. The sand sample contained 1.2 x 10³ cell L⁻¹, of which 30% were cysts. Cysts were very similar to those found at Sepetiba bay, south of the bloom area [6].

The toxin profile was dominated by Neo-STX, followed by GTX2 (Table 1).

Table 1. Toxin profile obtained by post column HPLC from *A. minutum* bloom collected on Rio de Janeiro Coast, 25/04/2007.

Toxin	Extract concentration ng/ml	Concentration in STX equivalent (%)
GTX 1	0	0
GTX 2	31.0	7.79
GTX 3	0	0
GTX 4	8.8	4.31
GTX 5	0	0
dc-GTX2	0	0
dc-GTX3	0	0
Neo-STX	130.1	83.47
dc-STX	0	0
STX	6.3	4.43

The toxin profile is similar to that observed for *A. minutum* isolated from New Zealand [7], in which Neo-STX also dominated, and distinct from European isolates in which GTX 4 was the major toxin [8].

This is the first report of vegetative cells of *A. minutum* from the Western South Atlantic. Among species of *Alexandrium*, *A. minutum* apparently occupies a broad niche, and has a large geographical distribution [9-11]. Its present regional and global distribution has been hypothesized to result from bio-invasion, as a result of ballast water translocation [11]. In fact, during a cyst survey for the Globallast project in Sepetiba bight, cysts of *A. cf. minutum*, among other, were reported in the region. Sepetiba is an important port subjected to large ballast water discharges, located about 80 km south of the bloom region. Considering a bloom as a manifestation of species opportunism, the fact that *A. minutum* vegetative cells were never before recorded in the region, and the fact that it was first reported as a cyst in a nearby

port area, the idea of ballast water introduction appears to be quite attractive to explain its presence in Rio de Janeiro waters.

Together with *Gymnodium catenatum* [12] and *Alexandrium tamarense* [13], this is third marine PSP producing species found in Brazilian coast. Although during the bloom no other harmful effect other than the aesthetic was observed, this species can affect the flourishing mussel aquaculture in the country.

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PLANKTON*NET: A new and improving tool for studying and monitoring Harmful Algal Blooms

Introduction

PLANKTON*NET is an online family of websites with information about all types of plankton. It is a source of authoritative information about plankton taxa, featuring images, schematics, taxonomic descriptions and glossaries, and soon also online taxonomic keys for different taxon groups. It is also a repository for historic and current distribution data of plankton organisms. Most of the PLANKTON*NET records deal with marine phytoplankton, including harmful algae, but we are also increasingly archiving information on additional taxa, particularly zooplankton and also on freshwater organisms e.g. cyanobacteria.

PLANKTON*NET currently consists of three sites (at the Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine

Research (planktonnet.awi.de), Station Biologique de Roscoff (planktonnet.sb-roscoff.fr/index.php) and University of Lisbon (plankton-net.fc.ul.pt), with two more sites being planned for autumn 2007).

In each of these sites data are entered by the core PLANKTON*NET group, also including the Natural History Museum in London and IPIMAR in Lisbon as important data contributing members, but also by a growing number of external contributors from locations all over Europe and beyond. After a very simple registration process, these external partners can enter their own images as individual images or, more commonly, as part of an image set. They can add and modify records and customize the web interface according to their own needs and requirements.

New features

In all areas of plankton taxonomy and ecology but particularly in the field of HAB research, access is required to a very large number of different online resources. The great diversity of information sources available to an online user can make it very difficult to extract the most up to date or the most relevant information for one's needs. PLANKTON*NET remedies this situation by offering both the opportunity to learn about the taxonomy and ecology of harmful algae as well as a facility for entering observational data from historic data sets as well as current research projects such as cruises etc. As PLANKTON*NET is not only populated by the PLANKTON*NET partners but also by a number of external contributors, this gives us the unique opportunity to produce an easily and openly accessible online inventory

The screenshot displays the PLANKTON*NET website interface. At the top, the logo 'plankton net @AWI' is visible. The main content area is divided into two panels:

- Panel 1: Search interface:** This panel shows a search bar with the text 'dinophysis acuta' and a 'search' button. Below the search bar, there is a list of search results for 'dinophysis acuta', including images from the 'Irish Sea', 'North Sea', and 'Baltic'. Each image is accompanied by a small thumbnail and the species name.
- Panel 2: Image set:** This panel shows a map of the Baltic Sea region with a color-coded distribution of phytoplankton. The map is titled 'IOW Phytoplankton monitoring' and includes a description of the monitoring program. Below the map, there are links to 'show images in this set' and 'show geographical positions for this image set'.

On the left side of the interface, there is a navigation menu with links to 'home', 'information', 'sponsors', 'contact us', 'cite us', 'open access', 'search', 'scientific names', 'images', 'last images', 'observations', 'classification', 'image sets', 'references', 'glossary', 'help', 'button guide', 'content', 'index', 'search help', and 'about software'. There is also a 'login' section with fields for 'username' and 'password', and a 'statistics' section showing 'GMT 2007-07-29 14:03' and 'images 2697', 'glossary 744', 'hits provider 408807', and 'hits images 416728'.

Fig. 1. Example of PLANKTON*NET layout showing two panels: one for searching images (showing a search result with images from three different locations), and one to browse through and open image sets. This layout is customizable. Panels can be closed and minimized/maximized. They can be moved up and down the screen e.g. to place data input forms and observation search forms adjacent to each other.

of harmful algae with comprehensive, accurate and up to date information, not only about the taxonomy of organisms but also about their distributions, which are of particular importance in HAB research. An exciting new development in this context is also the design of a central portal through which searches of information can be made in all PLANKTON*NET sites simultaneously. To further enrich the portal, links to a number of additional

online databases including library resources and databases containing environmental information are also being created, so that a search e.g. on a given species will retrieve all relevant records from PLANKTON*NET sites, literature references and available environmental information.

To organize the diverse and complex content now at the core of PLANKTON*NET, individual PLANKTON*NET sites have also been

redesigned to enable the user to draw the greatest benefit from the PLANKTON*NET resource:

1. A new interface: A panel structure has been established with all panels in one page (e.g. search and data input panels). This system is extremely flexible (each panel can be minimized, closed or be moved up and down the page to customize it). In this way one can for instance enter new terms in the glossary while also carrying out searches on glossary terms (Fig. 1).

2. Tagging: Users can now add their own tags (diatoms, open ocean, cultures, etc.) to facilitate custom-made searches.

3. Custom image sets: One image can now be part of several image sets. In this way a user can produce custom made sets of images, e.g. restricted to harmful algae, particular taxon groups or records from a particular geographic area that can be used in teaching or for other presentations.

4. New search engines The site includes powerful browse and search functions allowing the user e.g. to search for distribution records of a given species, or look for all records in a given geographic location. These search facilities can be used to quickly find information on, for example, scientific names, images or image sets and to browse through the classification tree. Images and distribution data can also be browsed alphabetically.

5. New taxon detail pages: These now include, in addition to images, links to classification trees and short taxa descriptions a graphical representation of all locations for which PLANKTON*NET records of the taxon in question exist (Fig. 2).

Future Plans

At present, while we already have the means for collating detailed distribution records for any given harmful species, this is restricted in terms of its graphical representation, to a display of locations at which a species occurred at some point in time. What we would like in the future is a facility that also allows us to follow the time course of development of a given species, and therefore potentially to track the direction in which a developing bloom is moving. To accomplish this PLANKTON*NET will essentially

Fig. 2. Example of a taxon details page showing the different components: 1. Enlargeable images, 2. Links to external resources, 3. Link to the environmental database Pangaea, 4. Brief taxon description, 5. Map showing the locations for which records of the species appear in PLANKTON*NET.

follow a two pronged approach: 1. The development of the necessary IT tools for mapping species data, and to further increase the data input facilities (e.g. to include toxin data) and 2. Collation of the data to populate the resource so as

to form a high resolution observatory that can then also give warnings about the occurrence of a given species. This obviously requires a large joint effort and we therefore seek and encourage collaboration with additional external

partners.

If you have any questions regarding PLANKTON*NET, would like to contribute data, or have any suggestions for improvements, please contact the PLANKTON*NET co-ordinator: Alex Kraberg (Alexandra.Kraberg@awi.de) or the local site co-ordinators.

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Updates on the User-Friendly Guide to Harmful phytoplankton (in EU waters)

The Identification of harmful algal species (HABs) is often impeded by the large number of sources of information, on the disparate taxonomic groups. Although books and guides exist that aid in their identification, resources still need to be developed to provide relevant, easily accessible, and current information on HABs; electronic resources are a logical direction. Over the last four years, we have been developing an online guide to harmful

plankton at *The University of Liverpool* that is globally accessed by 1000's of users (www.liv.ac.uk/hab/intro.htm). For a detailed description of the HAB site and its sister site on planktonic ciliates, see Kraberg *et al.* [1], Kraberg & Montagnes [2], and Strueder-Kypke & Montagnes [3]. In general, these sites have as their centre, a series of "data-sheets" (one for each taxon), but they also includes sampling and fixation methods, references, and a

glossary. Furthermore, the entire sites can be downloaded or saved and printed as pdf files. Thus they provide an easily updated, "user-friendly" repository of information for scientific, non-scientific, technicians, and students.

After a brief hiatus, where we lacked funds, the *Liverpool* HAB site is now being developed, thanks to 10 months of support by the Esmée Fairbairn Foundation. One of the main goals of our present work involves

adding and updating datasheets for species, making the resource more comprehensive. An element of this work includes mapping current and historical harmful algal blooms showing their

distribution and toxicity levels in an easily accessible format. This is done using NASA World wind software to produce global images akin to Google earth.

Further information is also needed

to improve this internet repository. Specifically our goal is to help researchers identify live and Lugol's-fixed samples. To this end we need to incorporate a greater selection of images into the datasheets and further details on key features and similar species. We also need to ensure that our identification criteria are accurate. These goals will only be feasibly reached through collaboration from the HAB community: we encourage researchers holding taxonomic information and expertise about harmful phytoplankton to visit our site and offer assistance. We invite collaboration, comments, and criticisms regarding the website. Interested parties should contact Naomi Downes-Tettmar, Email: n.downes-tettmar@liv.ac.uk.

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• Argentina

First detection of domoic acid produced by *Pseudo-nitzschia* species, Chubut coastal waters, Patagonia, Argentina

Fig. 1. Study area with sampling stations.

A Harmful Algal Blooms Regional Monitoring Programme has been carried out in Chubut coastal waters (Patagonia, Argentina) since the year 2000. This programme ranges over an extended shoreline (approximately 1,000 km) with bays and gulfs where shellfish

of information, detection of human consumers' intoxication cases in public health facilities, and closures to ban shellfish extraction and sales. The study area is located approximately between 42°00'–46°00' S and 64°00'–67°30' W.

Phytoplankton samples for

are extracted from natural banks, and where there are also mariculture activities. The programme includes monitoring of harmful algal blooms and marine environmental conditions, shellfish toxicity control, educational and training activities and dissemination

qualitative and quantitative analysis and environmental parameters are collected from 14 stations. Analysis for Domoic Acid (DA) toxins was added from October 2005. In the period August 2005 - August 2006, DA in net phytoplankton samples from Punta Pardelas and Bahía Camarones monitoring stations (Fig. 1) was detected in October 2005. Analytical procedures were based on Quilliam *et al.* [1] method, Solid-Phase Extraction (SPE) being added. DA concentration was 0.66 µg/100 ml in a sample from Punta Pardelas (Fig. 2), and at lower levels at Camarones (Fig. 3).

DA is a potent neurotoxic amino acid produced by some species of *Pseudo-nitzschia* genus which causes Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning. This can be fatal to human beings, sea mammals and birds after consumption of contaminated shellfishes or/and fishes. DA was

Fig. 2. Domoic acid chromatogram from Punta Pardelas sample.

Fig. 3. Domoic acid chromatogram from Bahía Camarones sample.

previously detected in continental shelf waters of the Argentine Sea (Southwestern Atlantic Ocean) in July 2000 associated with *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* in Mar del Plata, province of Buenos Aires. This neurotoxin was present in natural samples of phytoplankton, mussels (*Mytilus edulis*), and muscle tissue and gastrointestinal contents of anchovies (*Engraulis anchoita*) [2, 3].

Net samples were analyzed with a Wild M20 light microscope (LM) and a Jeol JSMT 100 scanning electron microscope (SEM), following Ferrario *et al.* [4]: *Pseudo-nitzschia fraudulenta* and *P. pungens* were identified. *P. pungens* showed strongly silicified and linear fusiform valves with distinctive pointed ends; interstriae are approximately equal in number to fibulae

(11-12 in 10 μm). The raphe is not interrupted by an interspace (Fig. 4a-c). *P. fraudulenta* exhibited weakly silicified and convex-sided lanceolate valves with rounded ends; interstriae (18-24 in 10 μm) are slightly denser than fibulae (16-24 in 10 μm). The raphe is interrupted by a larger central interspace (Figs. 5 & 6). This species is morphologically close to *P. subfraudulenta*, but *P. fraudulenta* can be discriminated by evaluating some morphometric data, such as numbers of fibulae and interstriae (approximately equal) and non-parallel lanceolate valve margins [5]. In the study area, *P. fraudulenta* was the most abundant species with a peak of 24,200 cells L^{-1} in Punta Pardelas; *P. pungens* was detected at both stations in low concentrations in qualitative samples.

Temperature, salinity, nutrients (nitrate + nitrite ($\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$), ammonium (NH_4^+), reactive phosphate (RP) and reactive silicate (RSi), chlorophyll a- and Secchi disk depths were determined at

Punta Pardelas and Bahía Camarones stations during the August 2005 - August 2006 period. At the Punta Pardelas site, temperature ranged from 10 to 16°C, mean salinity was 33.99 ± 0.14 psu ($n=11$). $\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$ were not detected from spring to autumn while the highest concentration (4 μM) was in winter. NH_4^+ ranged from 0.2 to 2.7 μM . Concentrations of RSi were lower than 1.1 μM from spring to autumn, with a peak of 4.6 μM in winter. Mean RP was 1.0 ± 0.2 μM ($n=10$). Chlorophyll a (records available only between November 2005 - April 2006) did not rise higher than 0.8 mg m^{-3} . Mean Secchi disk depth was 8 ± 1 m ($n=7$). At the time of DA detection in October, water temperature was 13°C (3°C higher than September) and salinity 34.04 psu. $\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$ and RSi were not detectable. These nutrient concentrations decreased 96.5% and 100% respectively between September and October 2005; NH_4^+ decreased 30%, and Secchi disk depth (11 m) increased 3 m.

At the Bahía Camarones site, (August 2005 - August 2006) temperature ranged between 8 and 15°C. Mean salinity was 33.55 ± 0.11 psu ($n=11$). Maximum of $\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$ (7.3 μM) was observed in winter;

Fig. 4. *P. pungens* (a-c). a, internal view of whole valve showing pointed poles. Scale = 20 μm ; b, Part of valve in internal and external view showing mantle. Scale = 5 μm ; c, valve apex, note the biseriate striae with round poroids. Scale = 5 μm .

Fig. 5. Light microphotograph from the October bloom of *P. fraudulenta* in Punta Pardelas. Scale = 40 μm .

Fig. 6. *P. fraudulentata*. Internal view of whole valve showing fibulae and central interspace. Scale = 10 μm .

most of the period concentrations did not rise higher than 3.5 μM and were not detectable in November and December 2005. NH_4^+ ranged from 0.3 to 2.5 μM and RSi from 1 to 5 μM . Mean RP was $1.1 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{M}$ ($n=11$). Mean chlorophyll *a* concentration was $2.0 \pm 0.3 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$ ($n=7$) and mean Secchi depth was $6 \pm 2 \text{ m}$ ($n=7$). At the time of DA detection water temperature was 9°C and salinity 33.65 psu. All nutrients decreased in comparison with September (RSi: 64%; NH_4^+ : 45%; $\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$: 34%; RP: 26%); Secchi disk depth (8.3 m) increased 2 m.

P. pungens and *P. fraudulentata* are known to be toxic. Both species co-

occurred during the spring bloom at the Punta Pardelas and Bahía Camarones stations where DA was detected. Blooms coincided with nutrient decreases and Secchi disk depth increases in both places. This is the first report of DA production in Chubut coastal waters (Patagonia). The high density of *P. fraudulentata* in the sampling area may indicate that it was the DA producer. In spite of the fact that during this event there were no harmful consequences, we believe that the monitoring programme in Chubut shellfish harvest areas must be continued.

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Professor Enrique Balech

On August 26th 2007, a few days after celebrating his 95th birthday, Prof. Enrique Balech died in Necochea, Argentina, where he spent the last 50 years of his life.

Enrique Balech Capdeville was born in Telén, La Pampa, Argentina on August 17th, 1912 in a family of French origin. He studied Natural Sciences at the Instituto Superior del Profesorado "J.V. González" in Buenos Aires, and specialized in marine plankton. In 1937 he became chief of the Laboratory of Protistology of the Museo Argentino de Ciencias Naturales "Bernardino Rivadavia". He later moved to Necochea as chief of the Estación Hidrobiológica Puerto Quequén, until he

was dismissed, in 1947, for political reasons. He then worked as a high school teacher to earn a salary, and continued his research while working from home. In 1951 he received a fellowship from the French Government and spent two months at the Station Biologique de Roscoff; as a result he published a pioneering paper on sand-dwelling dinoflagellates (Balech, 1956). He was later granted a John Simon Guggenheim Fellowship to work at the Scripps Institution of Oceanography, La Jolla, California, USA from 1957-1958 (Balech 1962). He published a paper on two new dinoflagellate genera, *Scrippsiella* and *Fragilidium* (Balech, 1959). In 1961 he was employed as a

Enrique Balech at Sherkin Island Marine Station, Ireland in 1989. As a result of this meeting his monograph on *Alexandrium* was published in English by this institution.

Professor at Universidad de La Plata (Argentina), and from 1962 to 1981 was named Researcher of the National Council for Science and Technology (CONICET). Professor Balech was also a member of the National Academy. Between 1964 and 1965 he spent almost a year as a Visiting Researcher at the Department of Oceanography of Texas A&M University, working with phytoplankton of the Gulf of Mexico, the Caribbean Sea, and Antarctica (Balech & El-Sayed, 1965; Balech, 1967). After all these travels, and despite the opportunity of a research position abroad, Prof. Balech decided to return to Necochea, where he was head of the Estación Hidrobiológica Puerto Quequén until he officially retired in 1982. He used to say that he became a full-time researcher after retiring, since it was then that he finally had time for his taxonomic work. In the 1960s, based on studies of dinoflagellates biogeography in the Southwestern Atlantic, he delivered a rather accurate description of the surface currents in this area (Balech 1965), which was confirmed by satellite imagery 20 years later. Enrique Balech authored a large number of publications. In his ‘opera magna’ (as he used to call it) on the dinoflagellates of the Southwestern Atlantic (Balech, 1988) he illustrated over 330 species, with information on their ecology and distribution. He wrote an illustrated identification manual on Antarctic dinoflagellates (Balech 1976) with descriptions of the species based on the many investigations of Southern Ocean plankton. During his long scientific career, he dealt with almost all dinoflagellate genera, describing new species and genera and providing detailed revisions. Just to mention a few: the work on the genera *Protoperidinium* (Balech 1973, 1974, 1994) and *Alexandrium* (Balech 1989, 1995). His monograph on *Alexandrium* (Balech 1995) includes descriptions and illustrations of all the species, a fundamental contribution to the taxonomy of this genus.

Prof. Balech developed his scientific career from the modest facilities of the Estación Hidrobiológica Puerto Quequén, and throughout all these years maintained the museum at

the Estación and the historical wooden house, sometimes even using his own money.

He used to visit the Museo Argentino de Ciencias Naturales in Buenos Aires on a monthly basis, bringing fresh news from Necochea, sharing the excitement of researchers on the latest scientific achievements and guiding the students in their thesis work. He was in contact with many scientists all over the world, always prone to scientific discussions and guidance and sharing his immense knowledge with many of us. His lessons went beyond plankton. He taught us that perseverance, tolerance, high academic performance, and solid scientific knowledge are all tools necessary to build a better world.

In addition to his successful career as a scientist he had many other interests. His love for humanity and understanding of people led him to promote the universal language Esperanto; he was a teacher of Esperanto and president of the Argentine League of Esperanto. He published several works in this language and even, in 1951, an Esperanto-Spanish dictionary. He was also a pioneer among environmentalists, and published a book in 1978 “Geocidio. La destrucción del planeta” where he proposed a new combination for *Homo sapiens*: *Homo stultus*, (from Latin, brainless, fatuous) due to the role of human beings in destroying our planet.

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Enrique Balech at the third International Conference on Toxic Dinoflagellates, St. Andrews, Canada, 1985 where he was awarded for his outstanding work.

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Friends and colleagues from all over the world.

Future events

NOVEMBER 2007

Course: Taxonomy of Recent Dinophyceae

Wattenmeerstation Sylt of the Alfred Wegener Institut für Polar- und Meeresforschung, List/Sylt, Germany, 18-25 Nov 07.

Organized by Malte Elbrächter.

Registration deadline: 15 Oct 07 (melbraechter@awi-bremerhaven.de).

Course restricted to 10 participants, aimed at people working or intending to work with dinoflagellates (students, technical assistants, scientists) with basic knowledge of dinoflagellates.

Further information: www.awi-bremerhaven.de/Benthic/CoastalEco/index.html.

JANUARY 2008

Regional Meeting on Future Focus and Cooperation in HAB Research. 2nd Asian GEOHAB Meeting

Nha Trang Vietnam, 28 Jan-1 Feb 08.

The meeting will provide an opportunity to develop further ideas and outlines of regional and national research relevant to GEOHAB, establish partnerships and identify research components that may merge into the GEOHAB Core Research Projects.

Abstracts submission: 1 May 07 - 1 Jan 08.

Registration deadline: 21 Jan 08.

Further info: www.geohab.info.

MARCH 2008

SPECIAL SESSIONS ON HABs AT THE 2008 OCEAN SCIENCES MEETING

Harmful Algal Blooms: Interactive Influence of Nutrient Competition, Differential Grazing, and Other Causative Factors

Orlando, Florida, USA 2-7 Mar 08.

Organizers: C.J. Gobler, W.G. Sunda and E. Granéli.

Presentations examining the effects

of resource supply, algal growth, mortality processes, and nutrient cycling on HAB dynamics are welcomed, particularly those which explore feedback interactions among these processes. Talks on how such processes and feedbacks interact with other regulating factors such as benthic/pelagic nutrient coupling, physical forcing, climate change, anthropogenic alterations of ecosystems, and life cycles of HAB species are also encouraged.

Abstract deadline: 2 Oct 07. Online submission is highly preferred at www.aslo.org/orlando2008.

Regional and Comparative Studies of the GEOHAB and ECOHAB Programs, 2008 Ocean Sciences Meeting

Orlando, Florida, USA, 2-7 Mar 08.

Organizers: P. Glibert, D.L. Meitiv.

Comparative studies of HABs that occur in similar ecosystems around the world can further understanding of HAB dynamics by establishing the existence of recurrent patterns and revealing fundamental processes governing population development and toxin production. The session will focus on synthesis papers that report on large scale regional HAB projects, or which apply comparative approaches for HABs in upwelling, eutrophic, coastal lagoon or highly stratified systems.

Abstract deadline: 2 Oct 07. Online submission is highly preferred at www.aslo.org/orlando2008.

APRIL 2008

9th Advanced Phytoplankton Course - Taxonomy and Systematics

Stazione Zoologica 'A. Dohrn', Naples, Italy, 5-26 Apr 08.

Applications deadline: 31 Oct. 07.

The Course aims at training and upgrading qualified students in the identification of marine phytoplankton species. It is planned for 20 participants and will consist of theoretical and

practical sessions, examining a broad collection of fixed, live and slide material provided by faculty and participants.

Honorary director: G.R. Hasle.
Scientist responsible: A. Zingone.
Contact: A. Zingone (zingone@szn.it).
Secretary: I. Canettieri (i.canet@szn.it).

Further info: www.szn.it/apc9.

OCTOBER 2008

Ciguatera and related biotoxins

Nouméa, New Caledonia, 21-31 Oct 08.

Workshop on the latest developments in ciguatera research, covering environmental influences, causative organisms and socio-economic and medical aspects. It will be held at the IRD Noumea Centre and the SPC symposium facilities, Noumea, New Caledonia.

Further info: www.ird.nc/ciguatera.

NOVEMBER 2008

13th International Conference on Harmful Algae 08

Hong Kong-China, 3-7 Nov 08.

ISSHA is pleased to announce the 13th Int. Conference on Harmful Algae. Supporting organizations include School of Science & Technology, the Open University of Hong Kong and the Association of Harmful Algal Bloom of South China Sea (AoHABSCS).

Further info: www.hab2008.hk.

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HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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